

Teleporting Robotics in Space and Time

The relationship between present message and past message is established by entangled photons. The decision of the Robot or mechanised object is changed in present in such a way that the decision in past of the computer is changed thus changing the position of the mechanised object in space and time. The project is classified under Systematic Invention Unit. It is classified under Time Defence System of SIU.

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The physical mechanism system will follow during their development and termination. This might allow to create information regarding their geometrical shape under mechanical stress and physical space conditions within their...

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